

ARCTIC PASSION

Deliverable 5.1

Description of a versatile benefit
assessment approach and
Arctic resilience societal
indicators for the pan-AOSS

Version 1

19 December 2022

101003472 | Arctic Passion

**ARCTIC
PASSION**

Work package

5 – Assessing Societal Benefits and Economic Impacts

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Status

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Dissemination level

Public

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Abstract

The purpose of Work Package 5 (WP5) in the Arctic PASSION project is to enable and demonstrate the valuation of selected information services provided by the creation of the pan-Arctic Observing System of Systems (pan-AOSS). The enablement includes the creation of conceptual designs for alternative valuation approaches fit for evaluating different types of information services engendering quite distinct types of benefits. The selected information services refer to Pilot Services (PSs) developed in Arctic PASSION, while it may also include service innovation ideas from observing system (OS) sensitivity experiments performed in WP3 and new services related to Shared Arctic Variable (SAV) proposals developed within Arctic PASSION. The conceptual designs developed in WP5 will be used to create a valuation tool, which is also meant to be a legacy product of the project. Finally, the demonstration of valuation of arctic information services and of the valuation outcomes will be conducted.

This report presents the first attempt to link societal benefits with PSs by the Value Tree Analysis. The strategy involved a first step where PSs developers were interviewed and took part in workshops to enable characterization of the PSs in terms of their inputs and outputs, expected user groups, and identified and conjectured benefits. The outcomes of the interviews and workshops were analyzed and used to create a first set of value tree components. The costs attribution to the OSs was based on previous studies on Arctic observation systems, while the weights of OSs components were assigned according to the share of the costs estimated for each PS. No weights were assigned to the links towards benefits, thus, they will be revised in the future.

The valuation of the services can account for other value bases than monetary or monetized ones, such as public health related indicators as well as ecosystem services and biodiversity related indicators. Similarly, ratings may be qualitative or ordinal rather than quantitative and cardinal. However, the larger the variety of value bases used the more complex it often will get to convey clear messages on changes in value and aggregate benefits generated. Fortunately, for a significant part of the different value bases conversion procedures towards monetized values exist, which could make comparisons easier.

Eventually it seems wiser to apply one overarching yet quite flexible valuation approach as to be represented in the valuation tool. The tool will be supported with additional guidance material for its use and for the use of supporting methods with respect to valuation as well as market scans and stakeholder interaction.

For any valuation to be meaningful it is however essential to collect sufficient information on the differential impact that the use of a service tends to bring on average for a user group, on the likelihood that potential users will start to use the service, and on factors that affect the scaling of a service. For several PSs that means that further work needs to be done regarding more precise identification of user groups and their requirements for use of the service.

1. Introduction

1.1 The study in a nutshell

The Arctic is more affected by climate warming than any other region in the world. To monitor the ongoing changes, to predict the evolution of climate system and to develop mitigation measures, we need a coherent observational system. The current observational systems for the Arctic environment are fragmented, incoherent, and not tuned to user needs. The purpose of the project Arctic PASSION is the co-creation and implementation of a coherent, integrated Arctic observing system: the 'Pan-Arctic Observing System of Systems', in short pan-AOSS. It aims to overcome the flaws in the present observing system by refining its operability, improving, and extending pan-Arctic scientific and community-based monitoring and the inclusion of Indigenous and Local knowledge, by streamlining the access and interoperability of Arctic Data systems and services, and by ensuring the economic viability and sustainability of the observing system for years to come.

The purpose of WP5 in the Arctic PASSION project is to enable and demonstrate the valuation of selected information services provided by the creation of the pan-AOSS. The enablement includes the creation in Task 5.1 of conceptual designs for alternative valuation approaches fit for evaluating different types of information services engendering quite different types of benefits. The selected information services refer to so-called Pilots Services (PSs) explored in WP4 of the project, while it may also include service innovation ideas from WP3 and new products related to Shared Arctic Variable (SAV) (Starkweather et al., 2021) proposals. In Task 5.2 the conceptual designs will be used to create a valuation tool, which is also meant to be a legacy product of the project. Finally, the demonstration of valuation of Arctic information services and of the valuation outcomes will be conducted in Task 5.3. Each Task results also in a Deliverable, i.e. Deliverables 5.1 - 5.3.

1.2 The scope and remit of this report

In this report, D5.1, the conceptual designs for valuation of different types of Arctic information services based on data and information about the historic, current and expected state of the ambient environment in (parts of) the Arctic are presented. The report explains how information was collected, processed, and based on what criteria and approaches alternative conceptual designs were devised. The informational prerequisites and consequences of choices for representation of particular types of value are discussed with respect to their implications for suitability and skill requirements of various valuation concepts. Eventually, the report proposes an overarching flexible design, which allows it to be implemented in the tool in Task 5.2.

In practice the valuation design and subsequent application is guided by the portfolio of eight PSs in WP4 of the Arctic PASSION project. In conjunction with these PSs, it will also consider the SAVs (Starkweather et al., 2021), sets of observables to improve tackling issues related to the themes as wildfire, permafrost and sea-ice, for which Expert Panels will be established during the project. Each of the SAV proposals is connected with the PS in the same thematic domain. The set of observations and products for each of the wildfire, permafrost and sea-ice themes will be identified by the Expert Panels, with participation of local and Indigenous experts, scientists, local or regional decision and policy makers, agencies, services, etc, depending on the thematic stakeholder groups and on the feedback and suggestions provided by the Roadmap for Arctic Observing and Data Systems (ROADS) (Starkweather et al., 2021) Advisory Panel. The

list of eight PSs (PS1 – PS8) is provided below. Throughout the report references will be made to these by their sequence number (PS1 PS8). Short descriptions of these PSs can be found in Appendix 1. Further detailing of the various PSs is provided in the sections on interviews and workshops and annexes related to these (Appendix 2 and 3).

The eight Pilot Services are:

- PS1 Arctic Service ‘Event Database of CBM Using Oral Histories, indigenous and Local Knowledge
- PS2 Pan-Arctic requirements-driven Permafrost Service
- PS3 State of the Arctic Environment Service
- PS4 Integrated Fire Risk Management (INFRA) Service
- PS5 Local Atmospheric Pollution Forecast Service
- PS6 Improving Safety for Shipping in the Polar Seas
- PS7 CBM for Arctic Marine Climate Change, Noise Pollution and Impacts on Marine Living Resource
- PS8 Lake Ice Service for Arctic Climate and Safety

The elicitation of service characteristics of the different Pilot Studies proved to be a challenging exercise for all parties involved. The novelty aspects of different Pilot Studies imply that in various cases quite some choices regarding service design, data resourcing and deployment approaches are still open or even not so much formulated yet. This means that in WP5 a gradual and flexible approach with respect to defining conceptual designs was called for. This also means that some of the characterization work of Task 5.1 will continue during Task 5.2 The interviews hitherto conducted also indicate a significant need for additional support beyond the valuation tool. We discuss that briefly in chapter 4.

1.3 The structure of the report

The report is structured in four main sections describing the valuation approach used to estimate the costs of observing systems, development and running costs of PSs and societal benefits that they produce including the economic benefits.

After this Introduction Chapter Two describes the defining elements of the valuation approach, being (1) what steers applicability and methodology choice (value base, purpose and scope) and (2) the principal complimentary approaches proposed, Value Chain Analysis (VCA) and Value Tree Analysis (VTA).

The third chapter illustrates for a few Pilot Services how the VTA, VCA and web traffic analysis can be used in this project. Both VTA and even more so VCA encompass additional methods for analyzing or conducting preparatory steps in these methods. Chapter Three also presents a summary of the interviews and surveys conducted and which functioned as a basis for applying VCA and VTA to selected PSs.

Chapter Four turns the guidelines of Chapter Two and the experiences of Chapter Three into a formalized description of the stepwise realization of the valuation of different Pilot Studies, accompanied by Pilot Study examples. Subsequently, this is summarized in a flowchart representing the preliminary conceptual design of the tool. In addition, suggestions for supplementary valuation related guidance to Pilot Studies is provided. Chapter Five offers the conclusions.

2. Points of departure

2.1 The Building Blocks of Valuation

Especially since the types of information services and their prospective uses are so different it is important to first make an inventory of what a valuation may entail. In other words, we need to ask:

- A. For *what purposes* will valuations be conducted in the case of pan-AOSS based information services?
- B. *What types of values* will be considered in those cases, and do we admit more than one value type within one valuation?
- C. *How* can we conduct valuations, in terms of valuation methodology and data collection?
- D. *By whom and for whom* such valuations are carried out, and what are the implications for tool design and resourcing of valuations?

Next to the evaluation of Pilot Services an assessment of the significance of new or improved contributions for the overall system, as represented by the **shared arctic variables (SAV)**, will be conducted.

A - Purposes

Valuation of information services may extend from pure academic interest to justification of an investment effort to establish a particular service and the required underlying information value chain (Anderson et al., 2015; Mouter, 2019). Considering the context of Arctic PASSION and the nature of the proposed PSs especially the following purposes are in principle relevant:

- **Review:** to obtain a better understanding of the benefit potential addressed by one or several related services, and of the critical conditions in the value chain for realizing a significant part of the potential; benefits may be expressed in monetized, social and/or environmental terms;
- **Product improvement:** to obtain a better understanding of the composition of the value chain and to identify means to improve the effectiveness of the value chain, e.g. by better interaction with existing and envisaged users;
- **Formal cost-benefit analysis (CBA):** to produce a formal cost-benefit analysis, including indicators for judging whether the volume of public resourcing of a project can be justified given the estimated net benefit flow over the course of the service lifetime;
- **Societal relevance and impacts:** to evaluate to what extent the use of the services creates wider socioeconomic, environmental or public health and resilience benefits, even if net benefits remain modest for service users themselves;
- **User specific or business model test:** to assess for what kind of users the service may be expected to generate benefits which exceed the cost incurred for that particular use; or more generally - to investigate the resourcing vitality of alternative business models.

For the key Arctic variables most of the above listed purposes can be relevant and may be even pursued jointly to underpin significance of considered SAVs. It is however important to operationalize the notion of significance in this respect.

B - Types of values

Even though valuation is rooted in economic approaches, it does not mean that only monetary values are considered. Furthermore, the same effect may be associated with various - not mutually exclusive - values. It remains important to realize that broad scoped monetization as well as parallel use of differently rooted indicators do have their weaknesses and may lead to inadequate ranking of alternatives (Fleurbaey & Blanchet, 2013). In principle the valuation can be based on:

1. monetary and monetized values and indicators derived from those; monetary values means that costs and benefits are based on (changes in) transactions which have a price; in many cases this can severely limit the inclusion of effects and therefore one can choose to monetize non-priced effects by means of several methods; this means that alongside health, social or environmental values effects can also be expressed in monetized terms;
2. human health related indicators, notably morbidity, mortality, and quality adjusted life years (QALY), and indicators associated with those (such as hospital admissions);
3. values reflecting social conditions, such as stability of livelihoods, empowerment (involvement in decision making), inclusiveness/equal opportunities, transparency (information access);
4. environmental values, such as indicators of biodiversity, level and quality of ecosystem services, extent of nature areas;
5. academic value, the produced information has notable significance for the progress in one or more science areas.

Table 1 gives an overview for which type of evaluations the different valuation bases are probably most suited. It should be kept in mind that applicability will always depend on the purpose, ambition level, assessment resourcing, and the available information, and is ultimately a case-wise decision. Furthermore, for the evaluation of the entire system, through shared arctic variables, a multi-criteria analysis (MCA) seems a more suitable valuation instrument. Such an MCA can contain results of valuations of constituent elements.

C - Valuation methods and their data requirements

As the Pilot Services are at different levels of maturity and are concerned with eliciting quite different types of benefits, quite a variety of approaches could be relevant. However, the number of approaches included in the tool needs to be limited. Other approaches can be mentioned in the accompanying manual.

A key point remains the clarification in what way(s) the information service makes a difference in:

1. decision making of the existing or envisaged user; or
2. in the efficiency of operations of the user; or
3. in the opportunity to provide a new good or service or serve a new, hitherto not served, client group.

Options 1 and 2 are quite often simultaneously relevant.

Differential impacts can be expressed in:

- in physical terms (changes in environmental or human health values), and/or
- in social indicator terms (changes in participation, access, trust levels, ...), and/or
- in monetized terms (change in physical terms x shadow price/WTP; replacement value; etc.)
- in monetary terms (changes in prices and transaction volumes) - this is probably less relevant, as single method, in this project

In practically all cases the differential effect has first to be assessed in non-monetary terms, based on appropriate modeling or statistical inference valid for the considered mechanisms. In some cases, the differential effect may have to be inferred through an expert elicitation process, such as Delphi (Green et al., 2007). Subsequently, if needed, the estimated differential effects can be monetized by means of methods appropriate for the context. Avoidance of health and damage risks can be assessed regarding the willingness to pay for a specified degree of avoidance. In case of environmental effects, options for monetized valuation are the cost of compensatory measures, the value of changed ecosystem services, or the cost of substitute nature area.

Table 1: Indicative suitability of different value bases with respect to purpose of the valuation

Valuation basis	Review	Product improvement	Formal CBA	Societal relevance	User type fitness	Business model
monetary	mostly both are used	Sometimes	both monetary and monetized	-	sometimes	sometimes
monetized		more common		if also monetized values needed	more common	sometimes
human health	if health application	if health application	sometimes as interim result	sometimes (as interim result)	if health application	if health application
social conditions		unlikely unlikely	sometimes as interim result (if service has social purposes)	one of these as key value (depending on service)	if prime goal is social	unlikely
Environmental conditions		if service is oriented to environmental protection	if notable env. effects or if environmental improvement is prime goal			if prime purpose is serving environmental decision making

The significance of the shared arctic variables (SAV) will be notably driven by the extent to which these enable the development, improvement and use of information services about the current and future state

of (elements of) the Arctic environment. Therefore, SAVs will be judged by their opportunity creating ability, which - at least initially - may be easier identifiable through physical and social/health effects, rather than the eventually arising monetized effects.

Table 2 provides a summary of our current level of understanding of the types of valuations and valuation bases applicable to the different Pilot Services. During the realization of Task 5.2 (tool implementation) we will obtain more precision and certainty about applicable valuation types and valuation bases. A 'X' stands for a significant and confirmed applicability. A '-' sign indicates an uncertain applicability (e.g. not mentioned by developer) or less significant applicability. The '?' sign indicates that the applicability is in principle significant, but its implementability is not yet determined). A more detailed description of applicability is given in Section 3).

Table 2: A summary of the expected applicability by Pilot Service, partly in conjunction with SAVs

Purpose of the information use	Application case		Impacts' valuation basis		
	Pilot Service	Shared Arctic Variable (SAV)	Physical	Social & health	Monetized
1. Decision making (reducing damage risk)	PS2	X	X	?	X
	PS4	X	X	-	?
	PS5		X	X	-
	PS6	X	X	?	X
	PS8		X		X
	<i>PS3</i> <i>PS7</i>				
2. Operational efficiency (resource saving)	PS2	X	X	-	?
	PS6	X	X	-	X
	PS8				?
3. Opportunities for new products and client groups	PS1			X	?
	PS2	X	X	-	X
	PS4	X	X	-	X

2.2 Tools for describing and analyzing information propagation and use

These several methods have in common that they describe a sequence of actions supported and connected by facilitating nodes (datasets, observation capacity, models, network links, user interfaces (visualization and search applications).

2.2.1 Value Chain and Value Chain Analysis (VCA)

The value chain is a concept which can denote *both* the representation of a set of consecutive stages of processing information and/or matter resulting in one or more products *and* a tool for analyzing value formation in productive activities of any kind based on the representation of the productive activities as a set of consecutive stages of processing information and/or matter. The term was coined by (Porter,

1985, 2008) and has been elaborated by many different scholars and practitioners. The value chain has become a popular concept to support different types of socioeconomic and managerial evaluations of weather and climate services (Anderson et al., 2015; Cortekar et al., 2020; Lazo & Mills, 2021). When using the value chain concept as tool for analyzing value formation and valuation of specific services, we refer to *value chain analysis* (VCA).

A value chain describes how - in a stagewise process - resources are combined to refine or enhance constituent components into products, or in this case to turn data into information and information processing formats. Resources encompass input data, models, human capital, ideas, interaction channels with internal and external actors, etc. A value chain may generate both interim products, which are further used in other (parallel) value chains, and final products used by so-called end-users typically active outside ambient environment information and forecasting nexus, such as agriculture, husbandry, fisheries, forestry, nature management, transport, urban planning and management, power supply, rescue services, etc. etc.

The consecutive segments of a value chain may all be residing in the same organization, but just as well be divided over several organizations. Moreover, even if the sequence of activities is technically the same, different value chains (service generation routes) resulting in the same products can exist side by side (figure 1). For example, a national meteorological office may be able to cater (almost) the whole chain itself or cooperate with both international organizations (e.g. ECWMF, Copernicus) *and* local organizations, not only to get observation input data, but also to help to communicate and tailor products to specific user groups. For important recurrently or continuously operated multi-actor and multi-segment value chains it may be worthwhile to establish a collaborative body which can better assume responsibility across the whole chain.

It should be realized that, even though VTA and VCA in general represent the same or at least similar sequence of information processing phases, in practice the methods tend to operate at different aggregation or abstract on levels. Since VCA demands pertinent information about the impacts of use (by end-users), it needs to focus on one or a few closely related services. VTA aims to show how upstream and midstream resources can contribute to and supplement midstream and downstream resources, and to what extent alternative resourcing channels would be possible. This also means that ‘value’ in value chain refers to the value generated for society thanks to improved decisions and operations based on the use of a well-defined information service (cluster), whereas value in value tree refers to the accumulation and branching of information resources when considering a comprehensive information domain, such as pan-AOSS.

Figure 2: The hierarchical elements of the Arctic Value Tree defined in (IDA-STPI and SAON, 2017).

In (IDA-STPI and SAON, 2017) Observing Systems (OS) are first linked to Key Products (KP), Services and Outcomes (KPSOs), which further link to Key Objectives (KO). KOs are connected to societal benefit sub-areas that form Societal Benefit Areas (SBAs) (Figure 2).

In the Arctic, experts participating in the IDA-STPI and SAON meeting defined 12 SBAs (Table 3). The SBAs are associated with four focus areas of particular importance for the Arctic society: Economy, Environment, People and Climate. Each SBA contains a number of key sub-areas, which in turn contain a number of KOs and these are further divided into KPSOs. The idea is that each KPSO has observational systems requirements and when these are identified, the societal benefits accruing from any observational system can be evaluated and compared by integrating their potential contributions over the twelve SBAs. The VTA developed by (IDA-STPI and SAON, 2017) represented a first attempt to systematically link observing systems to societal benefits in the Arctic. For each specific practical benefit, or KO, the KPSOs involved are identified and linked through the key observables to the relevant OSs. Going back up the value tree, they can be also linked to one or more SBAs. These activities are then divided into different KPSOs that may contribute to KOs and finally to sub-areas and SBAs.

Table 3: Societal benefit areas in the Arctic defined in (IDA-STPI and SAON, 2017).

SAON's Arctic Societal Benefit Areas (2017)	
	1. Disaster Preparedness
	2. Environmental Quality
	3. Food Security
	4. Fundamental Understanding of Arctic Systems
	5. Human Health
	6. Infrastructure and Operations
	7. Marine and Coastal Ecosystems and Processes
	9. Resilient Communities
	10. Sociocultural Services
	11. Terrestrial and Freshwater Ecosystems and Processes
	12. Weather and Climate

The initial SAON Arctic Observing Assessment framework publication in 2017 defined in addition to societal benefit areas, the SBA sub areas and the key objectives. The observing system, products/services and groupings completing a full value tree have been established by work by Strahlendorff et al (2019) for atmosphere and ocean physical variables. The full tree gives a framework for VTA in Arctic Passion (see chapter 3).

Also, Intervention Logic (Doussineau et al., 2021) has been considered, but it appears to be more useful in later stages (Task 5.3 'Pilot services impact assessments and generalization'), as it is more oriented towards policy evaluation. For example, In Task 5.3 it could be used to assess appropriate degrees of upscaling of certain information resources to enable upscaling of service output and associated benefits.

2.2.3 Links between Value Tree Analysis (VTA) and Value Chain Analysis (VCA)

VTA assesses the information propagation process in relation to servicing particular (clusters of) objectives. On the one hand this represents the technical representation of the value chain and certain technology combinations can often be associated with particular types of organization of observation and basic data processing (figure 3). On the other hand, VTA also indicates what is the (priced) resource use of the information propagation. Yet, mostly VTA does not include information input outside the realm of the ambient environment, such as on exposed social and economic endowments, which get more important in the downstream part of the value chain. In some cases, VTA could be extended with data on (potential) exposure and impacts, such as for example in permafrost monitoring services. Yet, in that case it is important to realize that the associated costs concern only the resource used for observing and projecting potential exposure and impacts, **not** the cost of the considered effects.

At least in theory VCA can interrogate VTA on the cost per considered segment and match them with figures on use and inferred value assessed in the VCA. The combination of the two approaches allows - in theory - to check whether:

- the benefits of services attributable to the considered segments exceed the associated cost in the segments

- whether costs and/or benefits change when a differently organized value chain is used
- to what extent costs and/or benefits change when a different combination of data sources and nodes (i.e. different tree) is used
- to what extent costs and benefits change by adding or reducing input elements in the VTA

Figure 3: Alignment of Value Chain Analysis and Value Tree Analysis.

2.3 Brief review on preceding work on valuation of (Arctic) information system use

One of the first VTA applications for Earth observation is described in the NOAA Observing System Integrated Analysis (NOSIA-II) Methodology Report (Helms et al., 2016), which focuses on the relationship between available observing systems and their impact on NOAA’s diverse services and scientific objectives. The need for the accounting of scientific and social benefits connected to the Earth Observation systems for the Arctic areas has been growing in the past decade and led to several workshops and reports publication. In the occasion of the First Arctic Science Ministerial conference in 2017 the IDA Science and Technology Policy Institute (STPI) and the Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks (SAON) co-hosted a workshop with experts from international, state, and local governments, industry, academia and non-governmental organizations to develop an international Arctic Observations Assessment Framework (IDA-STPI and SAON, 2017). The workshop achieved an international consensus on a comprehensive set of elements of value trees linking the Arctic observing systems with SBAs. Twelve SBAs were approved and linked to 41 SBA sub-areas, and 163 key objectives providing a framework to link specific Arctic observing systems to societal benefits. Such a framework was applied in the IMOBAR report

also connecting observing systems with societal benefits in several case studies, covering benefits related to sea ice, permafrost, biodiversity, sea level rise and human dimension (Dobricic et al., 2018). The study also tried to compare investment costs into the Arctic observing systems with selected monetary benefits, finding that they were about two times higher than observing system costs. Since modeling products (e.g., climate and weather models, reanalysis) deliver valuable information for the Arctic, their costs and societal benefits were as well included in the value tree for the 12 Societal Benefit Areas in a study published in collaboration with the Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI) (Strahlendorff et al., 2019). The focus of this work was to complete the international Arctic Observations Assessment Framework with observing systems and services to determine the value invested currently in this part of the value tree and its attribution to societal benefit objectives. The valuation of societal benefits to match costs with societal benefits still needs to be added for an economically complete Arctic observing value tree.

The relationship between the use of Sentinel satellite data on sea ice cover and the benefits resulting from their use has been recently investigated in a case study in Greenland (Buch et al., 2021). The report by the INTAROS project highlights the importance of designing and implementing a fit-for-purpose Arctic Observing System in synergy with numerical modelling for the generation of benefits in business areas as shipping, cruise industry and fishery in the Arctic Ocean (Buch et al., 2021). Appendix 4 provides a brief overview of some previous studies on benefits from Arctic observation systems.

However, a concrete and comprehensive mechanism for linking observing systems, data management activities and the identification of needs with societal benefit is complicated for all the Arctic. For such reasons, a roadmap process was developed within SAON called ROADS (Starkweather et al., 2021). Its first implementation was for establishing an Arctic Region Component of the Global Ocean Observing System (ARCGOOS) capable of collecting the broad, sustained observations needed to understand and predict Arctic environmental change (Lee et al., 2019). The study by the Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks' (SAON) (Starkweather et al., 2021) re-evaluated the need for a ROADS process oriented towards generating societal benefit within the Arctic region, with an emphasis on the inclusion of Indigenous worldviews. ROADS was described as a comprehensive concept, building from a societal benefit assessment approach like a VTA through which the most imperative Arctic observations—here described as Shared Arctic variables (SAVs)—can be holistically improved.

3 Interviews and characterizations

3.1 Approach

In order to populate the PS specific VTAs and VCAs first interviews and a few workshops were held to enable characterization of the considered services in terms of their inputs and outputs, envisaged user groups, and identified and conjectured (types of) benefits. The lessons from the interviews were used to specify the discussion items in the workshops (held during the 2022 General Assembly). The interviews and workshops together emanated follow-up actions with respect to (1) PSs not yet interviewed, (2) a survey among PS6 users, and (3) elaboration of PS8 use options and profiles in collaboration with PS8 coordinator. The cumulated material from steps 1 - 3 is used for specifying the conceptual design of the evaluation tool and its constituent building blocks in this deliverable (Figure 4).

The generally used questionnaire for the interviews as well as the workshop summaries are included as Appendices 2 and 3 of this Deliverable.

Figure 4: A summary of the consecutive steps underpinning the conceptual design of the evaluation tool

3.2 Interrogating Pilot Services developers and other stakeholders

The Arctic PASSION project aims at co-creating a coherent, integrated pan-Arctic Observing System (pan-AOSS) since the available ones for the Arctic are fragmented, incoherent, and not tuned to user needs. The proposed project approach includes the involvement of stakeholders and PSs developers in the process of understanding the needs of the people living and working in the Arctic. Interviews, surveys and workshops with stakeholders will further enable interaction with experts on Indigenous and Local Knowledge. The results of those interactions provide insights into service operations, technical and usage conditions.

The structured interviews were conducted during the past year and the PS developers were asked to answer a set of questions following a common scheme aiming at establishing (i) the motivation of each PS, (ii) the novelty of the PS and its expected future developments, (iii) the planned main users and (iv) the potential benefits generated by the PS. In particular, great importance was given to the questions focusing on the innovative sides of each PS and to the assessment of the additional usefulness and advantages generated by the PS products. The questions were also formulated to identify the main users of the PS products and to understand which are their major needs. The final part of the interviews was focused on investigating the societal and economic benefits generated by the development of the PS. The complete set of questions is presented in Appendix 2.

The developers of PSs had the chance to interact with each other through online meetings and the General Assembly which took place in Denmark in June 2022. More than 100 people as project team members, Advisory Board members, Indigenous communities' representatives, guests and European Commission representatives took part in the assembly in person and online. During the Assembly several workshops involving the PSs took place in order to present their activities. Two workshops investigated synergies among PSs. Each of the two workshops brought together two PSs with potentially shared societal benefits. The interview and workshops provided the basis for designing preliminary Value Trees for selected PSs presented in this section.

The developers of six PSs have been interviewed with the final scope of understanding and quantifying the benefits generated by each PS. The developers who took part at the first stage of interviews belong to PS1 *Arctic Service Event Database of CBM Using Oral Histories, IK and LK*, PS2 *Pan-Arctic requirements-driven Permafrost Service*, PS4 *Integrated Fire Risk Management (INFRA)' Service*, PS5 *Local Atmospheric Pollutant Forecast Service*, PS6 *Improving Safety for Shipping in the Polar Seas Service* and PS8 *Lake Ice Service for Arctic Climate and Safety*. For each PS, the interviews were conducted following a common set of questions introduced in Section 3.2 and presented in Appendix 2. However, due to the special nature of PS1 a set of more descriptive questions on local (Indigenous) populations and oral histories were posed, mostly related to recorded landscape, cryosphere and ecosystems past changes. The main outcomes from the interviews highlight that the PSs are partially based on existing services and are planned to be improved through the inclusion of forecast services and historical data series. In PS2 and PS6 such data appear to be mainly employed by the scientific community and professional users, while non-scientific local users seem to constitute only a small portion of the total data consumers. PS4, PS5 and PS8 strongly address non-scientific local users. Nevertheless, all PSs developers highlighted the necessity to increase the level of interaction with local communities in order to provide user-friendly products tailored to their needs.

The developed PSs are also considered to provide different typologies of benefits to their users and to the local population. In particular, the societal benefits are estimated to be mainly related to an increase of safety related to activities in the Arctic. For example, wildfire detection, pollution forecast, sea ice and lake ice mapping provide valuable information to local communities and workers. That information aims at improving the health and safety of local communities as well as the safety of commercial activities like shipping and fisheries. The development of the PSs is meant to provide user-friendly products (e.g., maps and web applications) giving almost real-time data with the objective of reducing the probability of injuries

and accidents happening in the Arctic. The economic benefits are, on the other hand, mostly connected to the improvements in activities efficiency and cost reduction. Data and maps providing the extension of sea ice, for example, improve the efficiency of shipping services finding the shortest route and reducing costs of economic activities.

The PSs also generate relevant scientific data regarding ongoing and past Arctic environmental and climatic changes as sea and lake ice extension, permafrost thawing, atmospheric pollution, wildfire frequency, etc. These new data produce additional benefits in the academic field since they could be considered as input for scientific studies to improve the knowledge of the Arctic system in the context of global warming. They may also provide feedback to Copernicus Services on their performance in the Arctic and possible improvements in monitoring and predicting the state of the Arctic environment.

3.3 Value trees

3.3.1 Value trees – cost attribution options

Below illustrative VTAs are presented for a selection of PSs. Next to depicting the information propagation process for a (set of) service(s) the VTA also indicates the approximate size of attributable cost for each information provision segment. So far cost attribution has been based on:

- unit-cost figures per facility or delivered unit
- volume figures on number of facilities or units available
- apportioning on the basis of share in volume of information flows / stocks (GB)

Cost attribution of joint facilities is a common problem in accountancy and lifecycle analysis (LCA). In those fields several alternatives are proposed and used, being:

- apportioning on the basis of physical amounts (of the throughput or of the units of installed (production) capacity)
- apportioning on the basis of the sales value of the resulting outputs in combination with physical shares in the realization of these outputs; value may be based on market prices or based on imputed values of non-market goods (e.g., embodied labor or cost of market substitute)
- apportioning on the basis of the sales value of the resulting outputs
- apportioning on the basis of the cost carrying capacity of the resulting outputs
 - based on the cost sensitivity of demand
 - based on the relative profitability of that output

3.3.2 PS1: Arctic Event Database of CBM Using Oral Indigenous and Local Histories

The OSs necessary for the development of the PS1 are represented by oral Indigenous Knowledge-Local Knowledge records of past events integrated with traditional OSs as satellites and monitoring stations used for reanalysis.

PS1 produces outputs for KPSOs provided to local communities: Sociocultural Activities, Environmental Information Services, Food Services, Research Services, Natural Resource Services, Ecosystem Services and Communities Services. The identified KPSOs are linked to the sub-SBAs that are connected to the SBAs

at the top of the tree. The societal benefits generated by PS1 are part of the following areas: Sociocultural Services, Environmental Quality, Food Security, Fundamental Understanding of the Arctic Systems, Marine and Coastal Ecosystems and Processes, Natural Resources and Terrestrial and Freshwater Ecosystems and Processes. For the PS1, 21 KOs of the development of Event Database were identified and linked to 12 sub-SBAs.

The OSs and KPOS cost estimates are based on the Arctic share of the observing systems and numerical weather prediction evaluated in previous reports (Dobricic et al., 2018; Strahlendorff et al., 2019). The cost assigned to each observing system is calculated as 1/100 of the Arctic share. The 1/100 factor was determined considering that only 1% of all the users of each observing system participate in PS1. The weights of the links at the bottom of the tree for OSs and KPSOs have been assigned to estimate the share of the cost of observations and reanalysis for PS1. The cost of recording oral histories has been calculated as a unitary cost summing up the costs of the interview, considering transportation and time spent by the interviewer, and the costs of the translation from local languages to English. From the KOs, up to sub-SBAs and SBAs links at the top of the tree, the same weights have been assigned since the tree's structure and will be revisited during future assessments.

Figure 5: Preliminary Value Tree for PS1. (due to the current graphical limitations of the Spatineo tool, the thickness of the connections should not be compared between different VTA figures).

Figure 5 shows a *hypothetical* value chain for PS1, which is based on interview information, but not necessarily represents all involved categories of actors and their coverage of different value chain segments. A key issue in PS1 is the enablement of a combination of very different types of information sources, notably indigenous and local ones as oral history or otherwise, so as to create richer and mutually better confirmed information repositories on longer term changes and their impacts in distant and recent past and thereby enable improvement of outlooks for the near- and longer-term future. The thereby

3.3.3 PS5: Local Atmospheric Pollutant Forecast

The bottom of the tree depicted in Figure 7 has been designed identifying the OSs and Copernicus air pollution forecasts necessary for the development of the local atmospheric pollutant forecast service (PS5). The OSs are first represented by Earth Observation satellites and ground atmospheric observations used for meteorological forecasts forcing nine Copernicus models. They further include satellite and in-situ observations of air pollution assimilated by Copernicus models. In addition, OSs include local in-situ observations that are directly used in the ANN. PS5 produces outputs for KPSOs provided to local communities: Air Pollution Information Service, Health Warning Service and High Air Pollution Level Warnings. The identified KPSOs are linked to the sub-SBAs and connected to the SBAs at the top of the tree.

The societal benefits generated by PS5 are part of the following areas: Environmental Quality, Human Health, Disaster Preparedness and Fundamental Understanding of the Arctic Systems. For the PS5, 15 KOs of the development of local air pollution forecasts were identified and linked to 7 sub-SBAs.

The OSs and KPOS cost estimates are based on the Arctic share of the observing systems and numerical weather prediction evaluated in previous reports (Dobricic et al., 2018; Strahlendorff et al., 2019). The cost assigned to each observing system is calculated as 1/100 of the Arctic share. The 1/100 factor was determined considering that only 1% of all users of each observing system participate in PS5. The weights of the links at the bottom of the tree for OSs and KPSOs have been assigned through the estimation of the share of the cost of observations and numerical model forecast for PS5. From the KOs, up to sub-SBAs and SBAs links at the top of the tree, the same weights have been assigned since the tree's structure and will be revisited during future assessments.

Figure 7: Preliminary Value Tree for PS5 (due to the current graphical limitations of the Spatineo tool, the thickness of the connections should not be compared between different VTA figures).

3.3.4 PS6: Improving Safety for Shipping in the Polar Seas

The flow chart in Figure 8 shows that some of the user domains also still need other information. In other words, the sea ice service is at best only a contribution to a value generating process, but possibly not crucial. Furthermore, the important segment ‘ocean prediction’ is an important feeder to marine services, but also services end-use sectors directly (and not only via marine services). On the other hand, the end-user groups ‘disaster resilience’ and ‘infrastructure and operations’ are very significant user groups for the sea ice service. In fact, one ambition may be to extend the services towards local communities via the user domain ‘marine and coastal processes’.

Figure 8: Preliminary Value Tree for PS6 sea ice services (due to the current graphical limitations of the Spatineo tool, the thickness of the connections should not be compared between different VTA figures).

3.3.5 PS8: Lake Ice Service for Arctic Climate and Safety

The preliminary Value Tree for PS8 depicted in Figure 9 was outlined in Donner (2022). The bottom of the tree, i.e., the connection between OSs and KPSOs, was formed by reading available documentation of the Lake Ice Extent (LIE) product.

The top of the tree, i.e., the connections between KPSOs, KOs, sub-SBAs, and SBAs, was formed by identifying which KOs are potentially realized from the usage of the Lake Ice service. The potential use cases for the Lake Ice service were identified by reading the Lake Ice Extent product’s documentation, by interviewing a potential user and by interviewing the developers of the LIE product and of the TARKKA service. TARKKA service is the interface where the LIE product can be viewed together with other earth observation datasets. Based on the identified potential use-cases, the relevant KOs reflecting these use-cases were recognized using the International Arctic Observations Framework. In total, 34 KOs were connected to the Lake Ice Extent service. These KOs were linked to 18 sub-SBAs which in turn were linked to nine SBAs.

The outline of the Value Tree is incomplete, as new earth observation products have been added to the Lake Ice Service after the writing of the thesis. The structure of the Value Tree for PS8 will be revisited during the assessment work. Moreover, the value flows need to be rescaled.

Figure 9: Preliminary Value Tree for PS8 (due to the current graphical limitations of the Spatineo tool, the thickness of the connections should not be compared between different VTA figures). Figure 10 shows a hypothetical value chain for PS8, which is based on interview information, web traffic scan, and a literature review. It nevertheless does not necessarily represent precisely all categories of actors involved and their coverage of different value chain segments.

In contrast to PS1, PS8 is building on an existing service. Therefore, initially the value creation of the current service version could be assessed, thereby making use of observed and reported data for costs, use and behavioral response. Subsequently, in collaboration with the service provider and stakeholders an elaborated service version can be defined. Some initial ideas have already been suggested in the first interviews. The identification of different (end-) user groups and their ways of using the information merits to be improved. It is possible that also in this service an indigenous service element will be added in collaboration with Sami organizations.

In this PS the costs of information provision are probably not the main issue, given the use of readily available information and portal, even though a significant addition with respect to indigenous information (both as input and output) may entail some cost. Furthermore, for that and other extensions stakeholder interaction and market review will be important in order to have more certainty the elaborated service does indeed create more value. In this value chain analysis, the challenge will be to properly identify and assess the purposes of information use and the extent to which the information eventually makes a difference in decisions and/or operations. Furthermore, in contrast to PS1 it is as yet not very clear what the feedback and learning could contain, but in situ citizen observations and photos are likely elements of such feedback.

energy...). From access log files, the IP addresses behind requests are anonymized. Using this anonymized IP address combined with information from geolocation databases, an estimation on the location of the user can be computed. Anonymization lowers the accuracy but ensures the method is mindful of privacy and related legislation. By identifying and visualizing this information of the users, it can be determined whether the service is being used in regions or sectors where the service would be most useful to users. Mapping the user locations and the volume of usage could help identify whether arctic communities have started using the service to an expected extent. In addition, the analysis can help identify some unexpected uses and benefits of the service. If the web traffic analysis reveals some unexpected activities in service usage it is possible to dig deeper into these use-cases with other assessment methods.

To ensure that the analysis meets the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) requirements, Spatineo has developed a free and open-source tool for the anonymization of log files. After anonymization, individual users cannot be identified from the IP addresses.

Other impact assessment methods are to be used combined with web traffic analysis, to get a comprehensive picture of the perceived benefits. Trends in service use give interesting insights into how much the service is used and by whom. However, it does not tell how much value or benefits the usage of the service generates to the user. Nevertheless, the results of the web traffic analysis could be used to target tasks related to other impact assessment methods better, e.g., interviews with users. The results are an important input to PS developers and could be used to e.g., target activities in service promotion better.

3.4.2 Pre-testing of the method

The method was tested in Isabel Donner's master's thesis (Donner, 2022). As a pre-study, the usage of the Lake Ice Extent for the Northern Europe (LIE) product, calculated and published by the Finnish Environment Institute, was analyzed. The LIE product can be viewed through the Finnish Environment Institute's TARKKA service. Detailed information about the usage of the product was obtained by analyzing service access log files. Please refer to the thesis for more detailed results.

The analysis shows that the number of requests has grown during spring months during the years under review (see Figure 11). This indicates that the users have been most interested in the product during ice break-off season. The number of requests by unidentified users has been high in the time between August 2019 and January 2020. This increase in requests could be explained by some applications that fetch data from the LIE data layer, as most of the unidentified requests originate from Amazon Web Service (AWS) cloud computing platforms.

According to the analysis, most of the users viewing the LIE product are in Finland (see Figure 12). Furthermore, as Figure 13 shows, most of the users are "general users", i.e., citizens and smaller companies whose IP addresses are linked to a telecom or internet service provider. 27% of the IP addresses could not be linked to any user group ("Not Available"). Out of these non-classified IP addresses, 87% can be linked to AWS cloud computing platforms. The users behind requests coming from cloud computing platforms cannot be identified.

Also, the spatio-temporal variability in the requested areas of the LIE product were analyzed. The analysis showed that in the beginning of spring, between February and April, the users are most interested in the lake ice extent of southern Finland. In May, however, there is a clear shift of interest as northern parts of

Finland become more interesting as well. This pattern in the variability in interest of different areas is repeated annually.

Figure 11: Identified user groups viewing the LIE product, separated monthly. No data was available for the time between 24th of January and 2nd of March in 2021.

Figure 12: Countries from which requests have been sent to the LIE product in TARKKA service. The pie chart is based on the total number of unique IP addresses per session during 1.1.2019–30.11.2021.

Figure 13: Identified user groups behind the GetMap requests made to the LIE product. The pie chart is based on the total number of unique IP addresses per session 1.1.2019–30.11.2021.

4 Conceptual design by project type

4.1 Analysis Introduction - basic steps and formats

Valuation steps to be conducted

1. **characterize the service** to be (e)valuated in terms of topic that it deals with, kind of information it provides, (envisaged) purpose(s) of information provided, and (envisaged) types of users;
2. **specify the information contents of the service for the end-user** (variables, spatial and temporal resolution(s), information quality indicators, renewal frequency); if relevant distinguish different quality levels;
3. **specify the information differential for users** when comparing service availability and its absence; and **specify the expected impacts** owing to (changed) decisions and/or operations - qualitatively or quantitatively
4. **specify the information sources and sourcing** alternatives - preferably by means of VTA, update cost information if possible and sufficiently relevant; do cost levels depend on ways of organization consecutive nodes? do alternative sources lead to other quality outcomes?
5. **specify the information sources and sourcing** alternatives regarding social and economic conditions, and environmental conditions (if not covered in VTA) necessary to evaluate consequences of decisions or actions in response to the use of the service;
6. **infer expected volume of use of the service**, preferably based on pre-existing or otherwise comparable services, preferably using the Spatineo Impact web traffic tool, possibly supplemented with interview or survey information; if relevant and possible compare outcomes for different quality levels and organizational designs
7. **choose one or more unit-values** for the volume of use and assess resulting aggregate value of the provided service (at a certain quality level); subtract attributable costs

4.2 Supplementary explanations on user and provider elicitation methods

ad.2) Assumption 1: for a given service there is no client specific tailoring, i.e., every user receives the same information; if service is provided in more than one version, each version is defined as an own product.

Information service x consists of an array of variables $[V1 ..Vn]$ describing aspects of the state of the physical environment in a georeferenced area(s) a at time(s) t . The frequency with which the service supply new versions of the variable array is called f (hours, days, weeks, years, etc.). A service delivery can now be defined as a set S , where $S_s [[V1 ..Vn]; [a1 ..am]; [t1 ..tk]]$;

Preliminary suggestions for quality indicators:

- distribution moments of the deviation between observed or predicted value/state and value/state observed by the user
- distribution moments of the deviation between observed (interpolated; bias corrected) value/state and value/state verified
- distribution moments of the deviation between predicted value/state and value/state later observed by OS

- ease of connectivity with other data for the user (no or minimal postprocessing needed prior to merge; NB! this may concern also non-EO data)

ad.3)

In absence of the service information a user has decision endowment D1

$$D1 = f(X_1 \dots X_z | \bar{V}_1 \dots \bar{V}_n) \text{ where } \bar{V}_n \text{ stands for the assumed value of } V_n$$

if service information is available the user has decision endowment D2

$$D2 = f(X_1 \dots X_z | V_1 \dots V_n) \text{ where } V_1 \text{ stands for the observed or formally predicted value of } V_1$$

$$\bar{V}_1 = V_1 + \delta_1 \text{ or } \bar{V}_1 = V_1^\delta$$

Utility of user i is defined as $U_i(D_j) = f_i(X_1 \dots X_z; \delta_1 \dots \delta_n)$,

where all $\delta_n = 0$ if optimally informed by service and $\delta_n \neq 0$ otherwise

Dj denotes decision endowment D1 or D2.

if $U_i(D_2) - U_i(D_1) - C(x) > H$ the user would be satisfied with the service; C(x) is the cost of acquiring and using the service; H is a threshold level (≥ 0) that is to be achieved

$$\text{if } U_i(D_2) - U_i(D_2) - C(x) > H$$

Uncertainty can refer to expected values of deviations and to expected values of utility outcomes.

Table 4. Formal description and example application side by side for subsequent valuation steps

	Formal description	Example application
1	Provide a textual description of the service – i.e. topic that it deals with, kind of information it provides, (envisaged) purpose(s) of information provided, and (envisaged) types of users.	
2	Information contents of the service An array of variables [V1 ..Vn] describing aspects of the state of the physical environment in geo-referenced area(s) a at time(s) t. The frequency with which the service supplies new versions of the variable array is called f (hours, days, weeks, years, etc.). A service delivery can now be defined as a set S, where Ss [[V1 ..Vn]; [a1 ..am]; [t1 ..tk]];	PS8 Lake Ice Service: Vt,x : extent of ice cover today in lake X Vt-n,x : extent of ice cover in lake X n days back PS1 indigenous populations' oral histories: V1 ..Vn : quantitative indications (point values; ranges) for phenomena 1 n derived from textual input V1 ..Vn : pseudo-quantitative indications (ratings) for phenomena 1 n derived from textual input

	<p>Variables may denote numerical data, pseudo-numerical data (e.g. ratings), qualitative data (textual descriptions)</p>	<p>V1 ..Vn : qualitative indications (characteristics) for phenomena 1 n derived from textual input NB! In case of oral history types of input the recorded narrative as such will also have value – i.e. preserving a cultural legacy</p>
3	<p>information differential for the user</p> <p>In absence of the service information a user has decision endowment D1</p> <p>$D1 = f(X_1 \dots X_z \bar{V}_1 \dots \bar{V}_n)$ where \bar{V}_n stands for the <i>assumed</i> value of Vn</p> <p>if service information is available the user has decision endowment D2</p> <p>$D2 = f(X_1 \dots X_z V_1 \dots V_n)$ where V_1 stands for the <i>observed</i> or <i>formally predicted</i> value of V1</p> <p>$\bar{V}_1 = V_1 + \delta_1$ or $\bar{V}_1 = V_1^\delta$</p> <p>Utility of user i is defined as $U_i(D_j) = f_i(X_1 \dots X_z; \delta_1 \dots \delta_n)$,</p> <p>where all $\delta_n = 0$ if optimally informed by service and $\delta_n \neq 0$ otherwise</p> <p>Dj denotes decision endowment D1 or D2.</p> <p>if $U_i(D_2) - U_i(D_1) - C(x) > H$ the user would be satisfied with the service; C(x) is the cost of acquiring and using the service; H is a threshold level (≥ 0) that is to be achieved.</p> <p>In many cases expected values of realization will be used and/or sensitivity analysis.</p>	<p>PS8 Lake Ice Service:</p> <p>δ_1 : if referring to more recent ice information, i.e for user i without service $\bar{V}_1 \sim V_n$ and hence providing V1 corrects the knowledge of ice extent by δ_1 ; the a priori value of δ_1 is a function of the probability that it exceeds a threshold value relevant to the user at time t</p> <p>$f\{P_i(\delta_1 > H_i X_{1,t} \dots X_{z,t})\}$ so it is a personal estimate (guess) that the possible correction is significant; the inclination to expect that may increase, if the penalty of neglecting the information is significant (e.g. making a useless trip to the lake) and adequate alternative sources for updates are few or require more effort. In practice this can be inferred by eliciting the explicit (money) or implicit (time use for information gathering) willingness to pay.</p> <p>PS1 indigenous populations' oral histories: Since there are quite diverse uses possible of this information the decision framework may vary as well. In some cases the merging of traditional and modern observation information may support discrete decision instances similar to PS8. More importantly it may enable enhanced or new operations of one or more actor groups with respect to certain livelihoods (fisheries; logistics; pricing of goods and services; insurance products; etc.). This requires a description of the value chain and its formalization (incl. production functions) to obtain valuation estimates. Alternatively, with respect to social and cultural values one could interview involved actors and possibly include a WTP or rating survey.</p>
4	<p>Specify the Pan-AOSS information sources</p> <p>For service specified as set S_s $[[V1 \dots Vn]; [a1 \dots a_m]]$ input nodes and data flows (per node)</p>	<p>VTA example for PS6</p>

	<p>are defined. The amount or cost of data per downstream node connected to the selected service as share of total downstream data or data cost. Upstream cost attributable to input information flows of service set S is CFF and is defined as a fraction of data flows following from the considered downstream or as a cost fraction of these data as identified with the VTA tool</p> $C_{FF} = \sum F_s / \sum F \text{ or } C_F = \sum C_F / \sum C$	
5	<p>user cost and non-pan-AOSS data</p> <p>Assuming that generally the information services are free of charge (which is the intent of Arctic PASSION) users may still incur cost due to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • own efforts W (time used to acquire, process and interpret information from PSs and possible other information sources) • acquisition of other data (e.g. impact related) OD • cost associated with ICT specific for the use of the considered services (software, hardware, connection cost) ICT <p>So, the cost for user i can be summarized as:</p> $C_i = f(W_{i,s} V1..Vn) + OD_i + ICT_i$ <p>and $W = T_{i,s}\gamma w_i$</p> <p>where T is time spent in hours (per year) on service use, w is the wage rate of the user (type) and γ is applicable fraction (of the wage rate, based on literature or valuation practices in the considered country). The default value is 0.25 based on travel time research literature.</p>	<p>For PS8 the visit numbers are known.</p> <p>In 2021 there were about 2200 individuals (as consumers) visiting the website and about 250 professionals (public and private sectors). For PS8 users are unlikely to incur particular use cost for this PS Pilot Service. Therefore, we assume only the time cost count.</p> <p>The median net hourly wage in 2021 was about 15 € (Statistics Finland). The value of time for professional use is rated at 40 €. The value of time is defined as %-share of the wage rate or hourly gross labour cost respectively. For citizens the share is 50%, for professionals 100% (VTPI 2022).</p> <p>Assuming the average website visit takes 0.1 hour (6 min.) for consumers and 0.25 hour (15 min) for professional users. The involved user cost in 2021 would amount to:</p> $(2200 \times 15 \times 0.5 \times 0.1) + (250 \times 15 \times 1.0 \times 0.25) = 4150 \text{ €}$ <p>The time use cost estimate functions also as a <i>lower limit</i> of the aggregate value of the service. If anyhow possible, it is however better to infer benefits from effects of operations and decisions.</p>
6	<p>Infer expected volume of use of the service, preferably based on pre-existing or otherwise comparable services, preferably using the Spatineo Impact web traffic tool, possibly supplemented with interview or survey information; if relevant and possible compare outcomes for different quality levels and organizational designs.</p>	<p>PS8 Lake Ice Extent:</p> <p>Indicator 1: Web traffic analysis showed that the product has been requested most frequently during spring, which suggests that the users wish to identify the timing of ice break-off and ice-free lakes from viewing the data. Requests made to the data layer are mostly made by “general users” (i.e., citizens and smaller companies) in Finland. Also,</p>

	<p>The analysis can be divided into following steps:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Define indicators, i.e in case of PS8: (1) web traffic data; and if possible impact indicators from surveys or interviews (2) <i>number and characteristics of avoided unuseful trips</i>, (3) <i>probability that user skips trip given data content and up-to-dateness</i> 2. Recognize data sources 3. Collect data 4. Combine and analyze data 5. Visualize information 6. Report results (and recommendations) 	<p>other user-groups like companies and public administration were recognized. The web traffic analysis gives more detailed information about whom are requesting the data and in what volumes.</p> <p>See chapter 3.5.2. for a more detailed explanation of how web traffic analysis was applied to analyze the usage of Lake Ice Extent product. Indicators 2 and 3 have not yet been operated in this conceptual phase. Based on a few interviews, possibly followed by pop-up survey request for TARKKA web visitors it should be possible to get e.g. an idea whether (1) unuseful trip avoidance is indeed a relevant benefit, (2) what tends to be the effect on trip decision using this PS8 information, and (3) what is the average travel time and distance of the (avoided) trip</p>
7	<p>Choose one or more unit-values for the volume of use and assess resulting aggregate value of the provided service (at a certain quality level); subtract attributable costs</p>	<p>For PS8 this is similar and kind of follow-up what is presented for step 5. Calculate the total number of avoided trips and their travel time and distance. From this the cost savings with respect to time and non-driven kilometers can be calculated.</p>

Figure 14 presents and visualizes the relations between inputs to the tool, information processing activities in the tool, and outputs from the tool by valuation process step. It also identifies the types of actions needed and types of information resources to used or linked. The stepwise structure is in principle the same for every PS that is fit for valuation, however the types of data and the supporting methods necessary are expected to differ across the PSs. Also updating of listed data sources and supporting methods may be expected after realization of the tool.

Figure 14. A generic conceptual design for the tool to be developed in Task 5.2

4.3 Supplementary guidance options

From the interviews emerged the fairly broadly shared need that not only a valuation tool but also guidance document would be highly appreciated, as many Pilot Service teams regard themselves less familiar with approaches and methods for investigating demand for particular information services in terms of fitness for use, skill requirements, use costs, etc. In addition, also recommendations and perhaps examples regarding stakeholder mapping were indicated as welcome additional elements in support of and in addition to the tool.

At least written guidance, including links to additional tools and examples elsewhere seems possible. We will elaborate this during Task 5.2.

5 Conclusions

The implementation of the pan-AOSS allows local communities and professionals to easily access a wide range of information regarding the Arctic through the development of Pilot Services. Such services provide different types of benefits to end-users and local communities. The link between Observing Systems, Pilot Services and societal benefits can be estimated by different tools like VTA. The economic value of societal benefits generated by the PSs can be partly evaluated by the Value Chain methodology.

This report presents the first attempt to link societal benefits with PSs by the VTA approach. The strategy involves a first step where PSs developers were interviewed and took part in workshops to enable characterization of the PSs in terms of their inputs and outputs, expected user groups, and identified and conjectured (types of) benefits. The outcomes of the interviews and workshops were analyzed and used to create a first set of value tree components such as OSs, KPSOs, KOs, sub-SBAs and SBAs. A value tree was designed with the FMI tool (Strahlendorff et al., 2019) for each PS. The costs attribution to the OSs was based on previous studies on Arctic observation systems. The weights of OSs components were assigned according to the share of the costs estimated for each PS. No weights were assigned to the links towards benefits; thus, they will be revised in the future.

The valuation of the services can account for other value bases than monetary or monetized ones, such public health related indicators as well as ecosystem services and biodiversity related indicators. Similarly, ratings may be qualitative or ordinal rather than quantitative and cardinal. However, the larger the variety of value bases used the more complex it often will get to convey clear messages on changes in value and aggregate benefits generated. Fortunately, for a significant part of the different value bases conversion procedures towards monetized values exist, which could make comparisons easier.

Eventually it seems wiser to apply one overarching yet quite flexible valuation approach as to be represented in the valuation tool, developed in Task 5.2. The tool will be supported with additional guidance material for its use and for the use of supporting methods with respect to valuation as well as market scans and stakeholder interaction.

For any valuation to be meaningful it is however essential to collect sufficient information on the *differential impact that the use of a service tends to bring* on average for a user group, on the likelihood that potential users will start to use the service, and on factors that affect the scaling of a service (number of users or total market size of the tool). For several Pilot Services that means that further work needs to be done regarding more precise identification of user groups and their requirements for use of the service.

APPENDIX 1 – Brief descriptions of the Pilot Services selected for the study

PS1 - Event Database of CBM Using Oral Histories, Indigenous Knowledge and Local Knowledge

The PS1 aims at developing the Event Database: a unique repository of past climate, ecological and environmental changes based on maps and written translation of Indigenous Knowledge-Local Knowledge observations from local languages into English, completed by reanalysis data when necessary. The PS1 Event Database will consist of a continuously uploaded database including written documents of oral records of past and recent/current changes in landscapes, cryosphere, ecosystems obtained from communities living in the Arctic areas of Alaska, Canada, Finland and Faroe Islands.

PS2 - Pan-Arctic requirements-driven Permafrost

PS2 will use satellite observations at high horizontal resolution combining high resolution observations of surface changes associated with abrupt permafrost thaw disturbances with observations of permafrost temperature and active layer in close collaboration with the local communities. PS4 will update the community-oriented maps following community evaluation and feedback and establish best practices for observations derived from community input defining the first global measurement standards for the permafrost Essential Climate Variable. PS4 will further serve the Arctic Council Working Groups, land managers, policy and decision-makers, and the scientific community.

PS4 - Integrated Fire Risk Management

PS4 will provide near-real time risks maps, early identification of outbreaks and short-term forecasts of the fire event evolution based on satellite and ground-based forest fire observations, weather forecast and observations of land and vegetation conditions. PS4 will co-develop the monitoring and forecasting system with Indigenous and local communities, using a modular approach to facilitate the implementation in different conditions.

PS5 - Local Atmospheric Pollutant Forecast

PS5 applies an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) model for improved air pollution forecasts combining observations from local stations and Copernicus forecasts. In particular, the ANN combines in-situ air pollution observations at several stations measuring atmospheric PM10 concentrations and PM10 forecasts by several Copernicus models to provide improved air pollution forecasts. Air pollution forecasts will be available on the Internet informing local communities, while information on Copernicus model performance will provide feedback to model developers and local and regional policy makers supporting decisions regarding pollution reduction and prevention.

PS6 - Improving Safety for Shipping in the Polar Seas

PS6 will develop an operational service quantifying the risk to a vessel as it navigates through ice-covered waters based on ice charts, automatic ice information products and relevant information based on in situ ship observations, buoy data and satellite observations. The PS Pilot Service will improve the POLARIS risk assessment methodology by analyzing historical ship traffic coincident sea ice conditions and extending the current method to add a forecasting capability. PS6 will include partners from the European Ice

Services and research vessel operators, along with guidance from the Arctic Council Working Group, PAME, the coastal administration, as well as industry representatives and maritime education establishments.

PS8 - Lake Ice Service for Arctic Climate and Safety

PS8 will use satellite and in-situ observations to provide maps on the Internet with near real-time information on the lake ice status for European areas where lakes get ice cover regularly or sporadically. Information on lake ice status is particularly important for communities living in the high latitude arctic or subarctic areas concerning livelihoods like reindeer herding and fishery, income by tourism industry, shortening distances due to the ice-roads and enabling access to the islands.

APPENDIX 2 – Questionnaire used for initial characterization of the pilot studies

1. Is the Pilot Service based on an existing service?

1.1 Is the novelty compared to the existing service(s) related to better quality (resolution) or more spatial coverage or some other improvement?

2. What are the development plans for the PS?

2.1 What kind of data will be available for users?

2.2 Are you going to combine different data sources? (e.g. Landsat, in-situ measurements, crowdsourcing...)

2.3 Are there any known issues?

2.4 To what extent does the use of the envisaged service require other information with crucial quality requirements so as to enable realization of the potential value added of the data service?

3. What are the planned main users of the PS?

3.1 Professional users? Non-professional users? Users for further research and model development? Users aiming at decision support of public and/or private organizations?

3.2 Can you give concrete examples of users?

3.3 Do you know any users that we could interview?

4. How are you planning to meet the needs of these various user-groups?

5. What benefits do you plan/estimate that users will get from the pilot service? Can you give concrete examples?

5.1 Economic benefits (e.g. economic savings, improved efficiency)

5.2 Societal benefits (e.g. improved safety)

5.3 Academic benefits (e.g. data as input to research)

5.4 Environmental benefits (e.g. protection of vulnerable sites)

6. Do you know of earlier explorations to quantify (some of) these benefit types with respect to Permafrost information?

APPENDIX 3 – Summary evaluation of Pilot studies in terms of fitness of valuation and lessons from the GA

Case no.	Service name	Interviewed?	Pre-existing (proxy) service? i.e. (almost) whole value chain exists already	Suitability for valuation
1	Event data base of oral histories	Yes	no	Will vary across use purposes
2	Permafrost monitoring service	Yes	yes	Promising
3	State of the Arctic Environment	No	entirely scattered	Low (too generic)
4	Wildfire (risk) warning & monitoring	Yes	no; some partial proxies	Better if use(r) is specified
5	Local atmospheric pollution forecast	Yes	no?; partial proxies	Still quite some uncertainties
6	Ice services for Arctic shipping	Yes	yes	Promising
7	CBM for Arctic Marine CC	No	no	Unsure
8	Lake ice monitoring & forecasting	Yes	yes	Promising (use purposes should be clearer)

Take-home message from the GA 2022

The scope of the valuation tool - guidance for the outlining in Task 5.1

- user needs mapping next to valuation etc.
- tool use contexts and consequences for methodological and indicator choices (interface consequences is an issue for Task 5.2)
- ‘real data based applications or also exploratory applications (just to check feasibility in principle)’
- also societal benefits, notably those envisaged by the users
- learning abilities of the tool; non-anticipated benefit; using results from earlier applications
 - consider to make the user needs mapping options supporting the valuation capability
- Polar Research Board gap analysis maybe useful

APPENDIX 4 – Conceptual design by project type

In the framework of the Arctic observing systems, several efforts have been performed during the last decade to identify key objectives and to assess the societal benefits derived from such services. Here we provide an extended version of the literature review presented in Section 2.3 focusing on the valuation of the Arctic information systems based on the most relevant publications on the topic:

- *International Arctic Observations Assessment Framework (2017)*. The report represents a common effort of IDA Science and Technology Policy Institute (STPI) and the Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks (SAON) to identify common objectives that rely on Earth-observing in the Arctic. The value tree presented in this report is a multilevel SBA value tree that establishes the connection between societal benefits and the set of Earth observation inputs that contribute to delivering those benefits in the Arctic. The main outcome of this work is represented by the definition of 12 SBAs located at the top level of the tree and define the environmental, economic, and social domains in which services, operations, and research provide societal benefit (see Table 3). Each SBA is subdivided into thematic sub-areas. For each area, the respective KOs are defined and represented by service, operational, or research activities linked to Earth-observing systems and their data and information products.
- *Impact assessment study on societal benefits of Arctic observing systems (IMOBAR) (Dobricic et al., 2018)*. This study proposes a new conceptual framework to link observations to benefits estimating the costs attributable to major observing systems in the Arctic. It also develops the links between observing systems, their outcomes and impacts on twelve societal benefit areas and a partial quantification of economic benefits for ten case studies. In particular, the core of this report is represented by the quantitative estimate of costs and benefits which led to two main challenges in terms of gathering information regarding the overall OS costs and determining the share of costs for OS not specifically designed for the Arctic.
- *Value tree for physical atmosphere and ocean observations in the Arctic (Strahlendorff et al., 2019)*. This report is based on a similar approach of the IMOBAR study, but it aims at describing in a comprehensive way the bottom levels of the value tree and at identifying next steps of products, like modelling, to answer all key objectives of the assessment framework. Its main purpose is to show the value invested currently in the OS and which part would be attributable to which societal benefit objectives. In this work the yearly unit cost of the OS and modelling components operating in the Arctic are estimated and connected to the value tree. The yearly values invested in the observation are also distributed between the 12 Societal Benefit Areas and their sub areas. The value tree tool developed by the FMI is flexible and available to address additional domains like atmospheric composition or biodiversity.
- *A Case Study: Navigation through sea-ice in Greenland (2019)*. This report focused on the analysis of the ‘Navigation through sea-ice in Greenland’ case study and is carried out in the context of the ‘The Sentinel Economic benefits Study’ (SeBS). This study aims at showing how OS products based on data generated by one or more Sentinel satellites deliver value to society and citizens. In this report the main outcome is represented by the demonstration of the value generated using OS to provide a sea ice mapping service. Each sub-case study highlights the relationship between the use of satellite data and benefits resulting from their use, including increased productivity, more efficient and environmentally friendly operations, economic gains, and improved quality of life.

- *Integrated Arctic Observation System (INTRAROS project, 2021)*. This report focuses on three selected business areas crucial for the Arctic: shipping along the Arctic Ocean, cruise industry in the Svalbard area and fishery in the Barents Sea. In each of those activities' business development planning, it is important to have reliable statistical information on key physical environmental parameters such as sea ice cover, wind and waves conditions, temperature and salinity of the water masses. The study presents examples of such statistics based on available data from OSI-SAF (satellite-based observations of sea ice) and Copernicus Marine Environmental Monitoring System – CMEMS (numerical model outputs). Its main aim is to highlight how crucial it is to design and implement an ad hoc Arctic Observing System to ensure the timely availability of high-quality in situ data needed for model assimilation, as well as validation of the quality of model and remote sensing products used both for statistical trend analysis and operational purposes.
- *Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks' (SAON) Roadmap for Arctic Observing and Data Systems (ROADS) (Starkweather et al., 2021)*. At the moment, there is no comprehensive planning mechanism for connecting and coordinating current observations and data management activities or identified needs. SAON identifies the need for ROADS to define a path to specify the needed observing and data systems and to detail how the various partners and players are going to collectively work towards achieving that system. The ROADS process is oriented towards the generation of societal benefits in the Arctic region, focusing on the inclusion of Indigenous communities' views in assessing that benefit. The ROADS guiding principle for shared benefit was improved at the AOS 2020, with an emphasis on the need for cross-disciplinary and cross-sector integration of observations that ideally tie into global observing frameworks. In addition, the AOS 2020 participants suggested adopting the term “shared Arctic variables” (SAVs) (Bradley et al., 2021) for the essential variables or processes developed under ROADS. Each SAV under ROADS should fully specify the observing and data system requirements from acquisition through high-impact information dissemination; this information should reinforce consistency and interoperability across the network. Activity under ROADS can be measured by the number of societal benefit areas that have been translated through SAVs into a consistent system of observing requirements and resource-estimated implementation plans and its success is measured through the realization of partnerships and investments to improve sustainment of Arctic observing and data systems in support of societal benefit.
- *A Framework for the Development, Design and Implementation of a Sustained Arctic Ocean Observing System (Lee et al. 2019)*. This scientific paper focuses on frameworks for systems aimed at “Planning/Policy” and “Strategy,” emphasizing the challenges associated with sustained observations over the larger temporal and spatial scales (years to decades, regional to pan-Arctic). The study also considers how such systems might be improved to provide tactical information and how frameworks might be designed to quickly integrate these needs into the design process. Such a roadmap was tailored for focus on the Arctic Ocean observing systems and the study advocated that the successful development and sustained operation of ARCGOOS requires a broadly supported framework within which essential observational targets and approaches are identified, the appropriate system metrics are monitored, and integrated data delivery systems developed.

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List of Abbreviations

AMAP	-	Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme
AOSS	-	Arctic Observing System of Systems
IL	-	Intervention Logic
KO	-	Key Objective
KPSO	-	Key Product, Service and Outcome
OS	-	Observing System
PAME	-	Protection of the Arctic Marine Environment
PS	-	Pilot Service
ROADS	-	Roadmap for Arctic Observing and Data Systems
SAON	-	Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks
SAV	-	Shared Arctic Variable
SBA	-	Societal Benefit Area
VCA	-	Value Chain Analysis
VTA	-	Value Tree Analysis
WP		Work Package